

AN ADAPTIVE METHODOLOGY FOR EFFICIENT MODELLING OF ARBITRARY DELAMINATIONS DURING CRASH SIMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In order to obtain good predictability in crash simulations of laminated composites, complex intra- and interlaminar fracture need to be captured. This requires detailed high-fidelity models where the separate layers are modelled individually, which is not feasible to use in industrial applications such as full vehicle crash simulations. In this paper we present the implementation of a single-layer shell element which can be adaptively refined in order to model intra- and interlaminar cracks. This way the high computational costs associated with the proper modelling of fracture in laminated composites can be limited in time and to areas where it is needed.

Using our methodology, we can reproduce similar results as a high-fidelity model while saving computational effort. This enables computationally efficient crash simulations of laminated composite structures, which in the long run help to develop crash structures made of laminated composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The introduction of fibre reinforced polymers (FRP) in the automotive industry is strongly dependent on accurate and efficient modelling tools to predict the correct energy absorption in crash simulations [1]. From experimental observations during axial crushing (see *e.g.* Hull [2] and Grauers *et al* [3]), it is obvious that in order to obtain good predictability in the simulations, delamination growth needs to be accounted for. Common practice to model delamination initiation and propagation is to model each ply by separate elements, interconnected by cohesive interface elements. However, due to restrictions on the simulation time, such high-fidelity models are not feasible to use in industrial applications such as full vehicle crash simulations. As a solution to this, we have previously presented an adaptive enrichment methodology for modelling of multiple and arbitrarily located delamination cracks using an equivalent-single-layer (ESL) shell model [4]. By utilising adaptive refinement, the computational costs associated with the proper modelling of fracture in laminated composites can be limited in time and to areas where it is needed.

Due to the extreme level of complexity, crash simulations are usually performed using dynamic explicit solvers. Any adaptive methodology must therefore be adapted to fit this type of solver. This poses a problem since explicit solvers are very sensitive to modifications like refinements during the simulation. Consequently, besides yielding accurate results and being computationally efficient, the implementation must be numerically robust.

Our adaptive methodology [4], previously implemented in the open source software OOFEM [5], has therefore been implemented as a user element in the commercial FE solver LS-DYNA, a well-accepted industry tool for performing automotive crash simulations. The implementation includes remedies to the instabilities that can occur when refining elements during a simulation in an explicit solver. Results show that we can have the similar prediction capability as a high-fidelity model while saving computational effort. We believe the use of adaptive refinements can enable computationally efficient large-scale predictive crash simulations of laminated FRP.

The work presented in this paper is a summary of two coming journal papers [6], [7] and we refer to these for further details on all topics presented below.

2 IMPLEMENTATION OF ADAPTIVE REFINEMENT METHODOLOGY

In summary our adaptive methodology consists of the following steps:

- i) The laminated structure is initially represented by a single layer of solid shell elements through the thickness;
- ii) Error identifiers are used to locate areas which need to be refined;
- iii) The shell elements are locally refined through the thickness by enriching the element kinematics with extra degrees of freedom (DOF) to account for material interfaces (weak discontinuities);
- iv) At interfaces prone to delaminate, cohesive zone (CZ) elements are inserted such that delaminations (strong discontinuities) can initiate;
- v) If the initiated delaminations propagate, the enrichment areas are expanded such that the fracture process can be accurately resolved.

This means that every adaptive element in the model can be in one of three stages: a) Unrefined; b) Refined in one or several material interfaces; c) Having one or several refined interfaces released, and CZ elements inserted. This is illustrated in Figure 1. In the following we will refer to the first type of refinement, where material interfaces are added through the thickness, as *weak refinements*. The secondary refinement type, where CZ elements are inserted, will be referred to as *strong refinement*.

Figure 1: The different stages of the adaptive element: In the unrefined stage the entire laminate is represented by one element through the thickness (a); The element can be through-the-thickness refined in order to model weak discontinuities as interlaminar interfaces, here exemplified with three refinements (b); The refined interfaces from the previous stage can be released (and have CZ elements added) in order to model strong discontinuities as delaminations (c).

Our implementation is based on a solid shell element (eight nodes with only translational DOF) where the refinements are represented using internal subelements, i.e. using an Augmented FEM (AFEM) [8] approach. However, as we stated already in [4] the adaptive methodology is not strongly dependent on the choice of either element formulation or enrichment technique, instead the key idea is that the delamination DOF are introduced only when and where they are needed during the simulation.

2.1 Element connectivity and internal force calculation

The base element consists of 8 vertex nodes. These base nodes are each associated with N so-called extra (or phantom) nodes, making a total of $8(N + 1)$ elemental nodes, where N is the number of active refinements in the element. Please note that the extra nodes are not element local. Instead, they are global like their parent base nodes and thereby shared between neighbouring elements. Furthermore, we want

to make it clear that unless the analysis input specifies otherwise, no refinements are present from the start. These are activated from within the elements when certain conditions are met during the simulation.

The extra nodes represent the surfaces of the internal subelements and their reference positions \mathbf{X} are assumed to be an interpolation of the bottom and top base nodes as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}_{8(i-1)+5} &= \mathbf{X}_{8i+1} = \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_1 + \alpha_i(\widehat{\mathbf{X}}_5 - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_1) \\ \mathbf{X}_{8(i-1)+6} &= \mathbf{X}_{8i+2} = \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_2 + \alpha_i(\widehat{\mathbf{X}}_6 - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_2) \\ \mathbf{X}_{8(i-1)+7} &= \mathbf{X}_{8i+3} = \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_3 + \alpha_i(\widehat{\mathbf{X}}_7 - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_3) \\ \mathbf{X}_{8(i-1)+8} &= \mathbf{X}_{8i+4} = \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_4 + \alpha_i(\widehat{\mathbf{X}}_8 - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_4) \end{aligned} \quad i = 1 \dots N, \quad (1)$$

where $\widehat{\mathbf{X}}$ are the reference positions of the base nodes and $|\alpha_i| \in]0,1[$ is a parameter which specifies the relative position of the interface with respect to the bottom and top surfaces. This means that, if a refinement is activated during the simulation its associated reference nodal positions will be calculated from the undeformed element. From Eq. (1) it can also be seen that we assume that each internal interface consists of two coinciding surfaces, defined by eight extra nodes. However, during the first weak refinement stage only one set of four extra nodes is active while an additional set of four is reserved for later use. If the interface is then strongly refined the reserved set of nodes is activated.

Furthermore, let \mathbf{x}_k be the current coordinates of node k . Then

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{u}_k \quad k = 1 \dots 8(N + 1), \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{u}_k is the displacement of the node. The displacements are calculated by LS-DYNA integrating the equations of motions using central-difference time integration [9]. In order to perform the time integration, forces (and masses) to all the degrees of freedom must be assembled by the user-element routine, which will be described next.

In each time step ${}^n t$ the LS-DYNA solver feeds the user element with the reference and current nodal coordinates \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{x} as well as the velocities \mathbf{v} . In return, the user element must give the element internal force vector \mathbf{f} . As seen in Eq. (1) and (2), the size of each of the elemental vectors is $8(N + 1)$, *i.e.* it depends on the number of active refinements N .

As mentioned above, the element can be in one of three stages. In the third stage some of the interfaces can be weak refinements while other represent strong discontinuities with CZ elements (strong refinements). This means that the full internal force vector \mathbf{f} of the element will be a sum of the forces from the currently active internal sublaminates and CZ elements \mathbf{f}^{lam} and \mathbf{f}^{coh} respectively:

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{f}^{\text{lam}} - \mathbf{f}^{\text{coh}}. \quad (3)$$

We will in the following refer to the sublaminates elements only as *subelements*.

In our model, each laminate layer is represented by one integration point through the thickness. Thus, for an unrefined element with $N = 0$ all layers are included in one single (sub)element representing the entire laminate. When the first refinement is activated ($N = 1$) extra nodes are assigned at the appropriate interlaminar position according to Eq. (1). The layers below the refinement are assigned to a lower subelement and those above to an upper subelement. Further refinement of a subelement ($N = 2$) would then divide the layers to new subelements below and above the refinement interface. This division of the layers is exemplified in Figure 2. Thus, the main challenge of calculating Eq. (3) is to gather the correct nodal positions and velocities and layer data for each subelement and then assemble the force contributions to the right places in \mathbf{f} .

Figure 2: Example of how an unrefined element with seven layers (left) is divided into sublaminae when the element is refined in interface two and four (right). The bottom two layers will be associated with the bottom subelement, layer three and four with the second subelement and the top three with a third and topmost subelement. The corresponding interface position vector will be $\alpha = [2/7 \ 4/7]$. The element base nodes are indicated with orange and the extra nodes with blue.

From the parent element \mathbf{X} , \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{v} we can extract corresponding subvectors associated with subelement i using projection matrices \mathcal{P} as

$$\mathbf{X}^{\text{sublam},i} = \mathcal{P}^{\text{sublam},i} \mathbf{X}, \quad \mathbf{x}^{\text{sublam},i} = \mathcal{P}^{\text{sublam},i} \mathbf{x}, \quad \mathbf{v}^{\text{sublam},i} = \mathcal{P}^{\text{sublam},i} \mathbf{v}. \quad (4)$$

The position and velocity vectors in Eq. (4) together with the sublaminate material properties (including material orientations) and integration point history data are then used to call an element subroutine which calculates the subelement internal force vector $\mathbf{f}^{\text{sublam},i}$ of the current time step. In our current implementation the element subroutine is basically the same as the LS-DYNA *PART_COMPOSITE_TSHELL element formulation 3, but with the assumption of equally thick layers of the same material system. Therefore, we will not give more details on the element formulation and how the forces are integrated, but refer to the LS-DYNA theory manual [9]. The material subroutine called from the element will be described in Section 3.

Once the sublaminate force is calculated it must be assembled in the element force vector. This can be done using the projection matrices above as

$$\mathbf{f}^{\text{lam}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} \mathcal{P}^{\text{sublam},iT} \mathbf{f}^{\text{sublam},i}. \quad (5)$$

If a weakly refined interface is to be released to a strong refinement we duplicate the interface and insert a CZ element. The nodal positions and velocities associated with the CZ element can be extracted in a similar way as for the subelements. That is, for an interface i

$$\mathbf{X}^{\text{coh},i} = \mathcal{P}^{\text{coh},i} \mathbf{X}, \quad \mathbf{x}^{\text{coh},i} = \mathcal{P}^{\text{coh},i} \mathbf{x}, \quad \mathbf{v}^{\text{coh},i} = \mathcal{P}^{\text{coh},i} \mathbf{v}, \quad (6)$$

where, once again, $\mathcal{P}^{\text{coh},i}$ are projection matrices.

Similar as for the subelements, the vectors in Eq. (6) together with the interface material properties are used to call a CZ element subroutine which calculates the internal force vector $\mathbf{f}^{\text{coh},i}$ of the current time step. To be specific, the CZ element subroutine is similar to the LS-DYNA solid element formulation 19 [10], an eight-node element with four in-plane integration points. Currently, material model 138 *MAT_COHESIVE_MIXED_MODE [11] is used. When the cohesive force is obtained it is assembled to the element force vector as

$$\mathbf{f}^{\text{coh}} = \sum_{i \in I} \mathcal{P}^{\text{sublam},iT} \mathbf{f}^{\text{sublam},i}, \quad (7)$$

where I is an array containing those interfaces which have CZ element.

2.2 Adaptivity

So far, we have presented the user elements connectivity and internal force calculation with respect to the different element stages shown in Figure 1. In this section we will describe when and how to go from one stage to the next.

In the first (weak) refinement stage we introduce weak discontinuities through the thickness, which will transform the ESL element into a layer-wise element. This way, better prediction of the out-of-plane stresses is achieved, and failure of individual layers can be modelled more accurately. However, initiation and propagation of delaminations are not possible and if this is needed there is a second (strong) refinement stage. In this stage, the weak discontinuities can be separated, and CZ elements are inserted.

Since the main purpose of introducing refinements is to improve the prediction of fracture we can consider several different error identifiers to determine when the element should be refined. For weak refinements this mainly include monitoring the intralaminar stress state. If the stress state is close to the failure initiation level, weak refinements should be activated.

In order to predict delaminations correctly, primarily two sources for these must be captured: high out-of-plane stresses and intralaminar cracks. The former can be considered by evaluating a cohesive failure initiation criterion at the interface positions. This requires a good prediction of the out-of-plane stresses, which is of low quality in the unrefined shell. In [4] we showed that a stress recovery technique can be used to improve the prediction of the stress state (of the ESL shell) and thus also of when to introduce strong (as well as weak) refinements. Furthermore, delaminations driven by intralaminar cracks can be captured by monitoring the intralaminar damage state. If a ply crack is beginning to form, strong refinements should be introduced adjacent to the crack. We want to emphasize that other error indicators could be added depending on which phenomena that should be captured.

As mentioned above, when a weak refinement is activated, a set of four extra nodes needs to be positioned to represent the interface, while an additional set is reserved for later use. The reference position \mathbf{X} of these nodes will be given by Eq. (1), but the current positions \mathbf{x} and velocities \mathbf{v} are unknown. In our model, we have chosen to assign these in a similar way as the reference positions, i.e. we interpolate the current positions and velocities from the closest active nodes below and above. Please note that these upper and lower nodes are not necessarily the base nodes, instead they could be other previously activated extra nodes. Please refer to [6] for details.

When a strong refinement is activated we duplicate the weak refinement interface by copying the current positions \mathbf{x} and velocities \mathbf{v} from the already activated set of extra nodes to the reserved set. The interface is now defined by eight nodes and a CZ element can be inserted in order to model delamination initiation and propagation.

2.3 Numerical stabilization

Both the weak and the strong refinements will result in a sudden change in the discretised internal forces. Since explicit solvers are very sensitive to sudden changes, this may cause non-physical oscillations in the model. To minimise these, we have implemented two types of damping procedures which will be explained below.

The source of the non-physical oscillations during weak refinement is that the interpolated positions (and velocities) of the newly activated extra nodes are likely not correct. So, in order to stabilise the refinement, we apply a small amount of damping for a short time period directly after the refinement.

To stabilize the strong refinement we here follow a method similar to that by Menouillard and Belytschko [12] and apply a correction force to balance the sudden change in forces. The purpose of the correction force is to tie the node pairs of the two coincidental interfaces together. The release of the strong refinements is made by gradually decreasing the tied force over a short time period.

2.4 Nodal mass

For LS-DYNA to perform the time integration, the correct nodal masses must be defined. During the initiation phase LS-DYNA will assemble mass to the base nodes by summing the contribution from all connected element. Since the extra nodes are not active during the initiation phase they are not assigned

any mass. Therefore, if a refinement is activated the mass of both the base and extra nodes must be updated to accurately represent the subelements they are defining. Each time a weak or strong refinement is activated we subtract the old mass of the unrefined (sub)element from the old nodes and add the appropriate mass of the new subelements to the old nodes and the newly activated extra nodes.

3 INTRALAMINAR MATERIAL MODEL

To limit the computational cost, we do not model intralaminar failure with separate DOF. Thus, our adaptive methodology only allows through-the-thickness refinements and not in-plane refinements. This means that we can model the initiation and propagation of interlaminar cracks explicitly but need to describe the intralaminar fracture in another way. We have chosen to use a so-called smeared crack material model [13], which assumes that the crack surfaces that form in each layer can be smeared over a representative finite element volume.

Ultimately, to properly model the intralaminar failure our intent is to use a state-of-the-art material model, *e.g.* similar to Maimí *et al* [14], Gutkin and Pinho [15] or Costa *et al* [16]. However, in this paper we have simplified the situation to only consider tensile matrix cracks using a single damage variable d . The material subroutine is similar to LS-DYNA material model 2 [11], *i.e.* an elastic orthotropic material formulated in terms of Piola-Kirchhoff stress \mathbf{S} and Green-Lagrange strain \mathbf{E} . The damage variable d then degrades the stiffness as

$$\mathbf{S} = (1 - d)\mathbf{C} : \mathbf{E}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the fourth order orthotropic stiffness tensor.

In order to evaluate failure initiation and damage evaluation we follow a similar approach as in [15]–[17]. The transverse and translaminar stresses are transformed to a potential matrix crack plane and a quadratic failure criterion is evaluated. If the criterion reaches unity the crack plane is considered fixed and used to evaluate the damage evolution. The damage variable is then calculated to ensure a linear degradation of the stresses until ultimate failure.

3.1 Regularisation of fracture energy

To smear the crack over the element volume there is the need for a length parameter L_e , which relates the imagined crack surface area A_c and the representative volume V_e of the element as

$$L_e = \frac{V_e}{A_e}. \quad (8)$$

The proper calculation of L_e involves determining the crack surface A_e , which is mainly a question of finding the orientation of the crack with respect to the element boundaries. However, there is also the need to consider a problem which arises when the crack surface is not aligned to the element mesh. In that case overlapping elements are activated in order to model a crack through the mesh. Then up to twice the amount of energy is dissipated compared to if the crack was aligned with the mesh. We have therefore added an additional correction factor, dependent on the inclination of the crack with respect to the mesh, to compensate for this. Please refer to [7] for details.

3.2 Interaction of smeared ply crack and delamination

The interaction of intra- and interlaminar failure is of special interest when using a smeared crack approach to model the intralaminar fracture and cohesive elements to model delaminations. Since there will be no explicit intralaminar crack tip present the interlaminar shear stresses are underestimated. This problem is illustrated in Figure 3 where we compare two methods for modelling intralaminar cracks and how they interact with adjacent interlaminar CZ elements.

To remedy this problem we have followed the approach by Yun *et al* [18], who suggest to reduce the critical fracture energy of a cohesive element using the damage state of the adjacent intralaminar elements, *i.e.*

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{G}_{Ic} &= G_{Ic}(1 - d_{\text{intra}}) \\ \hat{G}_{IIc} &= G_{IIc}(1 - d_{\text{intra}})^2\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

where d_{intra} is the maximum intralaminar damage of the adjacent elements and G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are the interlaminar fracture toughnesses, respectively.

Figure 3: Modelling the interaction of intra- and interlaminar cracks: To capture the discontinuous jump in shear deformation the CZ element should be separated at the ply crack tip. This requires modelling the crack with individual DOF (left); When using a smeared crack material model there is no explicit ply crack and the shear discontinuity is not captured in the CZ element (right).

4 RESULTS

We will in this section present numerical examples to verify that we can recover the same results as a reference model (standard LS-DYNA element) and reproduce experimental results. For choosing the parameters which control the refinements and the stabilisation thereof we refer to [6] and [7].

4.1 Triple cantilever beam

In our first numerical example we simulate a triple cantilever beam (TCB) where two mode I delaminations initiate and propagate through the beam. The beam consists of eight layers with material properties given in Table 1, all having the fibres along the beam. Since there is no pre-crack present we manually decide that refinements should be made in the second, fourth and sixth interface. The second and sixth are allowed to delaminate and the fourth is a material interface. The beam is loaded down- and upwards in one end and is clamped in the other end. To force two delaminations a symmetry condition is applied to the mid material interface (when active). An in-plane element size of 0.5 mm is chosen and to achieve stable delamination propagation we have assigned the CZ elements a high fracture toughness and low failure initiation strength, *c.f.* Table 1. To verify the results, we compare to a reference model made with standard LS-DYNA elements and materials (corresponding to those used in the user element). The beam, which is modelled with one element across the width is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Illustration of triple cantilever beam example. The beam, which has a length of $L = 50$ mm and thickness of $h = 2.048$ mm, is clamped in one end and loaded by prescribed displacement δ down- and upwards at the other end. Strong refinements with CZ elements will be added to the second and sixth interface (marked with black dashed line) and the fourth interface will be weakly refined and have a symmetry condition in the thickness direction (marked with red dot-dashed line).

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
E_1	100 GPa	σ_I	20 MPa
E_1, E_1	10 GPa	\mathcal{G}_{Ic}	400 J/m ²
G_{12}, G_{13}	5 GPa	k_I	5 GPa
G_{23}	4 GPa	σ_{II}	4 GPa
ν_{21}, ν_{31}	0.025	\mathcal{G}_{IIc}	0.025
ν_{32}	0.25	k_{II}	0.25
ρ	1600 kg/m ³	ρ_{CZ}	1600 kg/m ³

Table 1: Ply and interface material properties used in the TCB example.

In Figure 6 we have plotted the reaction force versus displacement for the reference, a non-adaptive and an adaptive simulation. In the non-adaptive simulation, the user element is refined from the start. In the adaptive simulation the refinements are made at a displacement level of $\delta = 0.0023$ mm. This corresponds to a failure initiation level of 1.0 in the outermost CZ element of the reference. If we instead evaluate the cohesive failure initiation criterion in using the intralaminar stresses of the unrefined element, we get a level of 0.48. This indicates that it is difficult to predict the failure initiation of the CZ elements using the intralaminar stresses. A knock down of 50% might be necessary. No damping or gradual release of the CZ element was needed to stabilise the solution and in Figure 5 the deformed beams are shown.

If we postpone the refinement to $\delta = 0.005$ mm, *i.e.* long after the reference CZ element failure initiation, there will be an unphysical propagation of the delamination, as is shown in Figure 7. By releasing the refinement over 0.01 ms the solution is stabilised, however, the force peak is a bit lower and postponed. We want to mention that the start positions and velocities of the extra nodes during refinement is likely rather good due to the through-the-thickness homogeneity. Instead, oscillations are the result of refining past the correct failure initiation level of the elements.

The main message from this example is that for many practical applications (*i.e.* more than one element) it might not be necessary to stabilise the refinement. If unphysical oscillations occur there is the possibility to stabilise the refinement with damping and/or gradual release. However, a better option is likely to make sure that the refinement is made before failure should have initiated.

 Figure 5: Deformed reference (left) and user element (right) beam at $\delta = 0.9$ mm displacement. The nodes which define the internal subelements in the user elements are visible as black dots.

Figure 6: Load versus displacement curve for TCB example. The user element with an initial refinement matches the reference exactly. The adaptive simulation shows a lower initial stiffness, but when refinements are activated at $\delta = 0.0023$ mm (vertical line in zoom), the curve begins to join the others. After the delaminations have started to propagate all models match very well.

Figure 7: Load versus displacement curve for TCB example. If the refinements are activated to late (vertical line in zoom), there will be an abrupt jump in the reaction force followed by small oscillations and an unphysical propagation of the delamination. By releasing the refinement over 0.01 ms the solution is stabilised.

4.2 Matrix-crack induced delamination

In a second example we have simulated matrix-crack induced delamination (MCID) in the four-point bending experiment performed by [19]. The material properties are taken from Reiner et al [20].

In Figure 8 we compare the load-displacement curves for simulations performed using a high-fidelity model with standard LS-DYNA elements and our adaptive user element with and without stabilisation. The user element is refined in the bottom 0/90-interface when the matrix failure index reaches unity in

the lowermost layer. Damping is applied for 0.2 ms (corresponding to 0.08 mm displacement change), which is followed by the release of the cohesive interface during 0.02 ms.

Figure 8: Load-deflection curves from simulation of a four-point bending experiment [4] where delaminations initiate from transverse matrix cracks. The adaptive simulations compare well with the reference high-fidelity model, however, without stabilisation unphysical oscillations will occur.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have implemented an adaptive enrichment methodology for modelling of multiple and arbitrarily located delamination cracks using an ESL shell model in the LS-DYNA explicit solver. The methodology includes stabilisation with consideration to the instabilities that can occur when refining elements during a simulation in an explicit solver.

Using our adaptive methodology, we can reproduce similar results as a high-fidelity model while saving computational effort since all degrees of freedom are not present from the beginning of the simulation. We believe the use of adaptive refinements can enable computationally efficient large-scale predictive crash simulations of laminated FRP. This will in the long run help to develop crash structures made of laminated FRP.

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REFERENCES

- [1] ERTRAC, European Roadmap Safe Road Transport, 2011.
- [2] D. Hull, A unified approach to progressive crushing of fibre-reinforced composite tubes, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 377–421, 1991.
- [3] L. Grauers, R. Olsson, and R. Gutkin, Energy absorption and damage mechanisms in progressive

- crushing of corrugated NCF laminates: Fractographic analysis, *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 110, pp. 110–117, 2014.
- [4] J. Främby, M. Fagerström, and J. Brouzoulis, Adaptive modelling of delamination initiation and propagation using an equivalent single-layer shell approach, *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 112, no. 8, pp. 882–908, Nov. 2017.
- [5] B. Patzák, OOFEM, 2000. [Online]. Available: www.oofem.org. [Accessed: 25-Apr-2017].
- [6] J. Främby, M. Fagerström, and J. Karlsson, An adaptive shell element for explicit dynamic analysis of failure in laminated composites – Part 1: Adaptive kinematics and numerical implementation, *To be submitted for publication*, 2019.
- [7] J. Främby and M. Fagerström, An adaptive shell element for explicit dynamic analysis of failure in laminated composites – Part 2: Progressive failure and model verification and validation, *To be submitted for publication*, 2019.
- [8] W. Liu, Q. D. Yang, S. Mohammadzadeh, and X. Y. Su, An efficient augmented finite element method for arbitrary cracking and crack interaction in solids, *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 99, no. 6, pp. 438–468, 2014.
- [9] LSTC, *LS-DYNA Theory Manual*, 02/20/19. 2019.
- [10] LSTC, *LS-DYNA KEYWORD USER'S MANUAL - VOLUME I*, 01/23/19. 2019.
- [11] LSTC, *LS-DYNA KEYWORD USER'S MANUAL - VOLUME II*, 01/23/19. 2019.
- [12] T. Menouillard and T. Belytschko, Smoothed nodal forces for improved dynamic crack propagation modeling in XFEM, *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 84, no. 1, pp. 47–72, 2010.
- [13] Z. P. Bažant and B. H. Oh, Crack band theory for fracture of concrete, *Matériaux Constr.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 155–177, May 1983.
- [14] P. Maimí, P. P. Camanho, J. A. Mayugo, and C. G. Dávila, A continuum damage model for composite laminates: Part I – Constitutive model, *Mech. Mater.*, vol. 39, no. 10, pp. 897–908, Oct. 2007.
- [15] R. Gutkin and S. T. Pinho, Combining damage and friction to model compressive damage growth in fibre reinforced composites, *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 49, no. 20, pp. 2183–2495, 2015.
- [16] S. Costa, T. Bru, R. Olsson, and A. Portugal, Improvement and validation of a physically based model for the shear and transverse crushing of orthotropic composites, *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 53, no. 12, pp. 1681–1696, May 2019.
- [17] P. Maimí, P. P. Camanho, J. A. Mayugo, and C. G. Dávila, A continuum damage model for composite laminates: Part II – Computational implementation and validation, *Mech. Mater.*, vol. 39, no. 10, pp. 909–919, Oct. 2007.
- [18] K. Yun *et al.*, A Damage Model Reflecting the Interaction between Delamination and Intralaminar Crack for Failure Analysis of FRP Laminates, *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 314, 2019.
- [19] D. J. Mortell, D. A. Tanner, and C. T. McCarthy, In-situ SEM study of transverse cracking and delamination in laminated composite materials, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 105, pp. 118–126, 2014.
- [20] J. Reiner, M. Veidt, M. Dargusch, and L. Gross, A progressive analysis of matrix cracking-induced delamination in composite laminates using an advanced phantom node method, *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 51, no. 20, pp. 2933–2947, 2016.